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The Non-Performing Loans at World Level

They decreased by 8.78% between 2010 and 2022

The World Bank calculates the percentage of nonperforming loans debts in total gross loans by country. Bank non-performing loans to total gross loans is the value of non-performing loans divided by the total value of the loan portfolio (including non-performing loans before the deduction of specific loan loss provisions). The loan amount posted as non-performing should be the gross value of the loan posted on the balance sheet, not just the past due amount. The data analyzed below refer to the period between 2010 and 2022. Countries with an incomplete historical series were excluded from the analysis.

Ranking of countries by value of banking non-performing loans on total gross loans in 2022. Equatorial Guinea is in first place by value of banking non-performing loans with a value equal to 55.41%, followed by Ukraine with an amount of 38.12 %, Chad with 27.70%, Ghana with 14.79%, Central African Republic with 14.51%. In the middle of the ranking, we find Malta with an amount of 3.70%, followed by Uzbekistan with an amount of 3.53%, Argentina with an amount of 3.09%, Paraguay with 2.94%, and Brunei Darussalam with 2.82%. The United Kingdom closes the ranking with 0.97%, followed by Estonia with an amount of 0.80%, Australia with 0.72%, the United States with an amount of 0.72% and Canada with an amount of 0.34%.

Ranking of countries by value of the percentage change of nonperforming loans to total gross loans between 2010 and 2022. Equatorial Guinea is in first place by value of non-performing loans to total gross loans between 2010 and 2022 with a value amounting to 1073.88%, followed by Uzbekistan with a value of 265.99%, Macao with 251.45%, Chad with 179.29% and Uganda with an amount of 176.13%. In the middle of the ranking there are the Kyrgyz Republic with a value of -15.72%, followed by Ghana with -18.18%, Madagascar with -23.34%, Nicaragua with -24.81%, and Russia with a value of -26.54%. Slovenia closes the ranking with a value of -78.69%, followed by Nigeria with -80.07%, followed by the United States with -83.68%, Estonia with -85.09%, and Latvia with an amount of -92.10%. On average, between 2010 and 2022, the value of bank non-performing loans as a percentage of total gross loans decreased by 8.78%.

Clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. Below we present a clustering with k-Means algorithm optimized with the Elbow method. The use of the Elbow method is made necessary by the fact that the k-Means algorithm is an unsupervised learning algorithm. Unsupervised algorithms require the use of objective criteria for optimization. Elbow's method is a graphical method

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to identify the optimal number of clusters using the k-Means algorithm. Three different clusters are identified, namely:

- *Cluster 1*: Russian Federation, Kenya, Gabon, Malta, United Arab Emirates, Mauritius, Kosovo, Uganda, Brunei Darussalam, Czechia, Slovak Republic, Macao, Canada, Lesotho, Papua New Guinea, Ecuador, Finland, Argentina, Georgia, Uzbekistan, United States, Turkey, United Kingdom, Cambodia, Panama, Indonesia, Mexico, Costa Rica, Paraguay, Netherlands, Malaysia, El Salvador, Saudi Arabia, Guatemala, Brazil, Nicaragua, Colombia, Peru, Estonia;
- *Cluster 2*: Greece, Ukraine, Equatorial Guinea, Cyprus, Chad, Central African Republic;
- *Cluster 3*: Bulgaria, Croatia, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Montenegro, Albania, Moldova, Ghana, Cameroon, Madagascar, Hungary, Slovenia, North Macedonia, Kyrgyz Republic, Nigeria, Latvia.

Considering the median of the cluster we note that the following ordering is $C2=21.10 > C3=4.62 > C1=2.13$. From a metric point of view, we can see that the value of cluster 2 in terms of median is about 4.5 times higher than the value of cluster 3 and about 10 times higher than the value of cluster 1. From a geographical point of view, we can see that the countries of cluster 2, i.e. the cluster that has the highest levels in terms of non-performing loans are European countries and central-southern Africa. It should be considered that the value of bank non-performing loans in Ukraine will probably increase further following the Russo-Ukrainian war. Cluster 3 consists of both European and African countries. These are countries that have significant financial fragilities that are substantially connected to the weaknesses of the reference economies. Cluster 1 is instead the cluster with the lowest presence of non-performing loans. Cluster 1 consists of European countries, North American countries, some Oceania countries. However, we note that within the countries of cluster 1 there are also countries that have low-average per capita incomes such as Kenya, Gabon, Uganda, Ecuador, Mexico. That is, the cluster of virtuous countries brings together both countries that have high per capita incomes and countries that have medium-low per capita incomes. This circumstance highlights the fact that the solidity of the banking system in terms of reduction of bank non-performing loans may not be connected to the overall economic performance of the economy, but rather to the application of a set of rules and efficient governance models.

Conclusions. The value of bank non-performing loans compared to total bank loans decreased significantly on average for the countries considered between 2010 and 2022 by an amount equal to -8.78%. There are some countries that significantly reduced the value of non-performing loans between 2010 and 2022. Among these countries are the United Kingdom with -75.36%, Slovenia with -78.69%, Nigeria with -80.07%, the United States with -83.68%, Estonia with -85.09% and Latvia with -92.1%. Certainly, the reduction in the value of bank non-performing loans is a positive fact. However, what worries the international banking system is the presence of off-balance sheet items and the creation of that "shadow banking" system which prevents bank balance sheets from being considered as reliable tools for assessing the efficiency of the credit system. Certainly the banks of the countries considered have demonstrated efficiency in reducing non-performing loans. However, the overall amount of risk placed in the shadow banking system is likely to have increased despite the reduction in global non-performing loans.

Declarations

Data Availability Statement. The data presented in this study are available on request from the corresponding author.

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Software. The authors have used the following software: Gretl for the econometric models, Orange for clusterization and network analysis, and KNIME for machine learning and predictions. They are all free version without licenses.

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Appendix

Country Name	2010	2011	2012	2013	2014	2015	2016	2017	2018	2019	2020	2021	2022
Equatorial Guinea	4,72	4,42	5,77	20,13	19,74	17,70	25,09	27,53	36,92	49,07	52,24	55,08	55,41
Ukraine	15,27	14,73	20,37	16,35	23,32	35,39	38,95	54,82	54,41	50,53	43,47	31,72	38,12
Chad	9,92	7,65	7,37	9,78	11,74	18,74	22,90	27,87	31,01	26,07	27,70	26,07	27,70
Ghana	18,08	14,15	13,20	12,00	11,27	14,67	17,29	21,59	18,19	13,94	14,79	15,12	14,79
Central African Republic	12,64	12,00	9,58	28,50	27,66	31,26	26,20	25,13	17,64	16,06	17,45	13,94	14,51
Cameroon	10,10	11,45	11,55	10,30	9,70	12,30	13,55	12,43	14,82	14,71	15,79	14,07	13,03
Kyrgyz Republic	14,78	9,40	6,55	5,09	4,18	6,74	8,52	7,37	7,30	7,73	10,09	10,82	12,45
Kenya	5,13	4,42	4,59	5,04	5,46	5,99	8,59	9,95	12,03	9,75	11,88	10,89	11,11
Madagascar	10,02	11,82	11,57	12,18	10,29	9,31	8,82	8,14	7,62	7,35	8,46	9,11	7,68
Cyprus	5,82	9,99	18,37	38,56	44,97	47,75	36,70	31,39	19,52	17,09	15,02	9,00	7,66
Gabon	3,16	2,78	2,55	2,74	4,07	9,14	9,03	11,80	15,73	9,23	8,96	7,61	7,64
Greece	5,62	9,20	15,72	27,81	29,99	35,71	37,36	45,57	41,99	36,45	26,98	9,16	6,53
Moldova	13,34	10,68	14,50	11,58	11,73	9,92	16,41	18,25	12,49	8,50	7,38	6,13	6,44
United Arab Emirates	5,27	6,09	7,13	5,85	5,31	4,75	4,80	5,00	5,26	6,03	7,57	7,29	6,39
Montenegro	20,93	15,29	17,30	20,31	18,59	14,58	11,35	8,29	7,36	5,09	5,87	6,83	6,33
Russian Federation	8,31	6,63	6,06	6,02	6,81	8,38	9,24	9,66	9,75	8,83	8,26	6,72	6,10
Uganda	1,86	2,04	4,06	5,97	4,05	5,13	10,40	5,51	3,34	4,75	5,22	5,19	5,14
Mauritius	2,76	2,81	3,64	4,15	4,92	7,20	7,76	7,03	6,52	4,94	6,21	5,82	4,92
Albania	13,51	18,05	21,19	22,24	21,46	16,84	16,55	11,97	10,43	7,97	7,65	5,39	4,79
Papua New Guinea	1,92	2,08	2,16	1,80	2,09	3,08	2,50	2,77	3,73	3,79	5,33	6,16	4,78
Bulgaria	11,92	14,97	16,63	16,88	16,75	14,61	13,17	10,43	7,80	6,62	5,80	5,94	4,63

Bosnia and Herzegovina	11,42	11,80	13,47	15,12	14,17	13,71	11,78	10,05	8,77	7,41	6,12	5,78	4,54
Croatia	11,59	12,93	14,56	16,76	18,43	18,17	15,04	12,14	10,41	7,41	7,63	5,70	4,33
Lesotho	3,03	2,10	2,46	3,79	4,23	4,04	3,69	4,42	3,66	3,30	4,20	4,07	4,31
Peru	1,87	1,84	2,17	2,53	2,87	2,83	3,04	3,26	3,27	3,37	4,13	3,91	4,12
Nigeria	20,14	5,77	3,71	3,39	2,96	4,86	12,82	14,81	11,67	6,03	6,02	4,93	4,01
Hungary	10,04	13,68	16,04	16,83	15,62	11,66	7,42	4,17	2,47	1,51	3,95	3,66	3,85
Ecuador	3,32	3,15	3,69	3,53	3,58	4,40	3,96	3,31	2,95	3,15	3,60	3,73	3,73
Malta	7,02	7,09	7,75	8,95	9,05	7,10	5,29	4,07	3,36	3,21	3,66	3,44	3,70
Uzbekistan	0,97	0,71	3,05	2,82	2,10	1,46	0,74	1,20	1,28	1,48	2,06	5,13	3,53
Argentina	1,84	1,23	1,54	1,53	1,79	1,57	1,70	1,73	2,96	5,70	4,15	4,29	3,09
Paraguay	1,40	1,84	2,20	2,12	1,97	2,59	2,94	2,81	2,51	2,56	2,41	2,27	2,94
Brunei Darussalam	6,87	6,03	5,38	4,53	3,85	4,00	4,75	3,66	3,92	3,90	3,87	3,11	2,82
North Macedonia	9,04	9,52	10,11	10,94	10,81	10,31	6,29	6,10	5,04	4,62	3,26	3,13	2,79
Cambodia	3,14	2,29	2,22	2,30	1,62	1,59	2,13	2,07	1,99	1,55	1,82	1,74	2,71
Brazil	3,11	3,47	3,45	2,86	2,25	2,85	3,08	2,88	2,60	2,66	1,87	2,08	2,64
Panama	2,65	2,14	1,95	1,87	2,21	2,20	2,52	3,05	3,26	1,96	2,01	2,25	2,53
Colombia	2,86	2,50	2,76	2,78	2,92	2,85	3,12	4,18	3,43	3,15	3,67	3,03	2,47
Indonesia	2,31	2,01	1,68	1,61	1,97	2,32	2,77	2,44	2,21	2,34	2,64	2,64	2,15
Costa Rica	1,86	1,82	1,75	1,75	1,55	1,66	1,55	2,05	2,12	2,40	2,41	2,26	2,11
Mexico	2,33	2,45	2,53	3,36	3,13	2,60	2,15	2,15	2,11	2,20	2,56	2,05	2,09
Turkiye	3,49	2,58	2,74	2,64	2,74	2,99	3,11	2,84	3,69	5,02	3,89	2,98	1,98
Kosovo	5,70	5,60	7,16	8,13	7,96	5,83	4,66	2,93	2,57	1,93	2,47	2,13	1,94
Slovak Republic	5,37	5,31	5,16	5,16	5,20	4,71	4,35	3,63	3,12	2,96	2,57	2,12	1,86
El Salvador	3,83	3,45	2,83	2,29	2,31	2,25	1,97	1,89	1,85	1,72	1,57	1,83	1,80
Saudi Arabia	2,97	2,22	1,67	1,31	1,08	1,24	1,38	1,61	1,95	1,86	2,18	1,86	1,78
Latvia	22,29	14,05	8,72	6,41	4,60	4,64	6,26	5,51	5,29	5,00	3,09	2,47	1,76
Slovenia	8,21	11,81	15,18	13,31	11,73	9,96	5,07	3,20	6,01	3,36	3,02	2,06	1,75
Malaysia	3,35	2,68	2,02	1,85	1,65	1,61	1,61	1,55	1,47	1,52	1,57	1,68	1,72
Netherlands	2,83	2,71	3,10	3,23	2,98	2,71	2,54	2,31	1,96	1,84	1,88	1,73	1,61
Nicaragua	2,04	1,91	1,88	1,98	1,00	0,89	0,86	1,04	2,43	3,10	3,70	2,45	1,54
Georgia	5,92	4,53	3,68	3,03	3,03	2,71	3,45	2,78	2,68	1,93	2,27	1,88	1,51
Czechia	5,46	5,29	5,35	5,26	5,64	5,44	4,52	3,68	3,10	1,69	1,91	1,70	1,46
Macao SAR, China	0,39	0,34	0,19	0,09	0,12	0,12	0,20	0,23	0,22	0,24	0,35	0,64	1,38
Finland	0,51	0,46	0,45	0,44	0,85	0,93	1,05	0,73	0,95	1,51	1,45	1,47	1,35
Guatemala	2,11	1,61	1,34	1,19	1,29	1,35	2,05	2,32	2,18	2,20	1,83	1,73	1,25
United Kingdom	3,95	3,96	3,59	3,11	1,65	1,01	1,69	1,36	1,10	1,02	0,98	0,97	0,97
Estonia	5,38	4,05	2,62	1,47	1,39	2,77	2,18	2,38	1,55	1,97	1,64	1,09	0,80
Australia	2,15	1,97	1,70	1,37	1,01	0,89	0,95	0,86	0,90	0,96	1,11	0,91	0,72
United States	4,39	3,78	3,32	2,45	1,85	1,47	1,32	1,13	0,91	0,86	1,07	0,81	0,72
Canada	1,19	0,84	0,65	0,57	0,52	0,52	0,60	0,45	0,51	0,50	0,53	0,38	0,34